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Methodology of teaching english language

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Abstract. Controlling the quality and effectiveness of English language lessons is manifested in the fact that the main part of the received information is taken from everyday life in speech expressions. Evaluation of the use of innovative technologies in the lesson as a tool for language teaching and learning helps to create many positive results and advantages.

Key words: Methodology, innovation, English language, communication, skills, competence, didactics, intercultural communication

Методика преподавания английского языка

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Аннотация. Контроль качества и эффективности уроков английского языка проявляется в том, что основная часть получаемой информации берется из повседневной жизни в речевых выражениях. Оценка использования инновационных технологий на уроке как инструмента обучения и изучения языка помогает создать множество положительных результатов и преимуществ.

Ключевые слова: Методика, инновация, английский язык, коммуникация, навыки, компетентность, дидактика, межкультурная коммуникация

Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and teacher's and student's activities, and have an important aspect in its implementation. Interactive methods are called group thinking, that is, methods of pedagogical influence, which are a component of educational content. One of the unique features of interactive methods is that they are implemented in cooperation with the teacher and students, through joint activities. Such cooperative activity is the basis for expanding students' knowledge and developing communicative and speech competences. The use of innovative

technologies is reflected in the work carried out to increase students' thinking, imagination, outlook, and interests. According to McCarthy, "the methodology of teaching foreign languages has evolved greatly over the past half century. At different times, grammatical translation, audio-linguistic structure, global audiovisual, inductive/deductive, functional, ideational, situational, communicative, immersion, carried out in learning/acquiring, recommending, etc." Consequently, as a result of the use of audiovisual tools during the lesson, the ability to remember the semantic meaning of words and use lexical units improves. Advanced modern technologies, innovative approaches and interactive methods ensure that students are highly educated and widely qualified. It should be said that in order for students to learn the English language, they must have knowledge, skills, and competences in the grammar of this language.

Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. He studied the classification of innovation process participants, their attitude to innovation, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific areas. "Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that affected our country as well. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. As a result of this, our President named this year as "Year of Youth Support and Public Health", which increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be wrong to say that the widespread application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the field of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time of increased international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country

usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and neighbors of other nationalities.

The subject of the methodology is the process and methods of education through the subject of a foreign language, the science of teaching a foreign language, the study of teacher and student activity is considered the subject of the methodology. The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics - what do we teach? is the content of teaching. Methodology - how do we teach? means educational methods and methods. The concept of method - methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and means the ways leading to a certain goal, the meaning of the method. In various literature, you can find the narrow and broad meaning of the term. "Methodology The term " in a narrow sense refers to the concept of education related to the concrete lesson process. It is interpreted as a controlled lesson process that includes instructions related to the planning of lessons and the preparation of educational materials. "Method The term "in a broad sense refers to the selection, classification and distribution of educational material. In the Federal Republic of Germany, since the 1960s, "didactics" and "methodology" have been used in a narrow sense. Accordingly, the content of didactic education What is taught? How are educational methods taught? z is the process of forming a person's personality by applying it to his cultural life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools are seen as educating the privileged few.

In the process of applying the method of communicative didactics, the teacher's method of forming intercultural communication is formed. As a result of learning a foreign language, the culture of a foreign country is also learned. In order to acquire the necessary knowledge in foreign language education, "exercise organization technology" is of great importance.

Practice is the best way to master all knowledge. The exercise gives a positive result not only in foreign language education, but also in mastering knowledge in all fields. Effective organization of the lesson, the role of the pedagogue and modern pedagogical technologies in it is incomparable. It is

important to organize the process of learning English with a communicative approach, to bring the next level to the level of intercultural communication, and to achieve such results, it is important to pay attention to the last step, "exercise technology". In order to effectively organize the English language teaching process, it is necessary to acquire knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

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